

Functionalized lipid nanosystems as therapeutic strategies for photoaging and chronological skin aging

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The skin is the most exposed organ to extrinsic and intrinsic factors that contribute to the manifestation of aging signs. Chronological aging results in dryness, epidermal thinning, and fine wrinkles, while photoaging, primarily caused by ultraviolet (UV) radiation, leads to deep wrinkles, skin laxity, and irregular pigmentation. A common underlying factor in both processes is the excessive accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which induce oxidative damage of biomolecules and accelerate skin aging. Natural antioxidants, such as resveratrol (RSV), offer promising protective effects against skin aging. However, poor stability, susceptibility to UV degradation, and limited skin penetration, due to the *stratum corneum* barrier, are limiting factors to achieve its antiaging potential. To enhance RSV stability and skin distribution its encapsulation on lipid nanocarriers is essential. Moreover, the efficiency of RSV delivery can be potentiated by using an active targeting strategy directed to aging skin biomarkers. A notable example is the targeting of $\alpha\beta3$ integrin receptors, which are overexpressed on senescent cells, using the RGD peptide. Additionally, liver X receptor agonists, such as T1317, promote keratinocyte differentiation and mitigate aging-related skin manifestations.

RSV was encapsulated in three lipid nanocarriers (DPPC, DPPC:Chol, and DPPC:Chol:DOPE) that were further functionalized with the target ligands (RGD and T1317). Characterization studies revealed hydrodynamic sizes ranging from 113 to 150 nm and zeta potential between -6 and +20 mV. Importantly, all nanocarriers remained stable over three weeks of storage. Encapsulation efficiencies exceeded 64%, with the highest observed in the DPPC:Chol nanocarriers. Incorporation of the lipid nanocarriers into a semi-solid pharmaceutical base ensured pseudoplastic behavior of the formulation, essential for cosmetic application and skin spreading.

Future studies will evaluate the *in vitro* therapeutic potential of these formulations, aiming to develop an effective, targeted anti-aging strategy for cosmetic applications.

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